

by strong culms and large and dark green leaves. It grows well in light acid sulfate soils, but has a rather long growth duration. Nang-thom sel. meets all the requirements of Asian rice consumers (Table 1). Gross income for Nang-thom sel. is about 50% higher than that for Nang-huong-ran sel. and other common scented rices.

More than 40 samples of 22 scented varieties were collected from 11 provinces in the south and screened in a 4-yr project.

The two new varieties confirmed yield and grain quality superiorities over cultivars in testing in relatively large areas during two recent seasons (Table 2). □

Table 2. Yields of scented varieties in on-farm trials in Vietnam.

Cooperative	Yield (t/ha)		
	Nang-thom sel.	Nang-huong-ran sel.	Check ^a
Thanh Loc (Ho Chi Minh city)	3.6 (135)	3.9 (150)	2.6 (100)
An Lac (HCM city)	3.4 (118)	—	2.9 (100)
An Phu Tay (HCM city)	3.0 (125)	3.5 (137)	2.4 (100)
My Le (Long An Province)	3.3 (115)	3.8 (131)	2.9 (100)

^a Local scented varieties. Figures in parentheses are % of local check.

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Molecular basis for puffing quality of rice

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High-amylose varieties such as Bhavani and IR50 are preferred for making puffed rice. We compared the molecular properties of amylose and amylopectin in Bhavani and IR50 with those in CO 25, ASD7, and Ponni, which are preferred for making rice flakes, *idli*, and cooked rice.

The amylopectin of Bhavani showed a longer chain than the other varieties studied (Table 1). The chain length of amylose was not determined.

The amylose and amylopectin isolated from these varieties were treated with

Table 1. Amylose percentage and chain length of amylopectin in rice varieties.^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Amylose (%)	Chain length (no. of glucose/branch)
Bhavani	30.0	26
IR50	27.6	23
CO 25	27.3	22
Ponni	27.2	22
ASD7	29.5	21
LSD	0.48	0.95

^a Each value represents the average of triplicate analysis.

Table 2. Percentage hydrolysis of amylose and amylopectin by salivary α -amylase at different time intervals.^a Coimbatore, India.

Variety	Component	Percentage hydrolysis at indicated time				
		30 min	60 min	120 min	240 min	360 min
Bhavani	A	51.8	62.1	66.2	86.0	93.2
	AP	50.0	59.6	59.6	61.9	65.3
IR50	A	49.7	65.3	79.0	84.9	88.0
	AP	48.2	50.4	51.8	56.2	65.3
Ponni	A	41.4	53.6	65.0	79.7	83.9
	AP	48.2	48.9	49.4	55.7	62.1
ASD7	A	43.5	51.8	60.1	66.2	66.2
	AP	38.3	43.5	49.4	56.9	57.9
CO 25	A	21.8	34.7	43.3	50.8	54.9
	AP	38.3	44.2	52.2	59.0	66.2
LSD	A	0.7 (between varieties)				
	AP	0.8 (between varieties)				

^a Each value represents the average of duplicate analysis. A = amylose, AP = amylopectin.

alpha-amylase and the amount of reducing sugars released was measured across time. The rate of release of reducing sugars from the amylose of Bhavani and IR50 was faster than in the

other varieties (Table 2). For amylopectin, the rate of release of reducing sugars was faster for Bhavani. □

High-yielding aromatic rice variety GR101

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GR 101, selected from segregating

material of IR8/Pankhali 203 cross, was released in 1986. The new variety has maintained its superior performance at all locations (Table 1). It has yielded 4.1 t/ha, 83.6% more than Pankhali 203.

GR101 has long, slender, fine grains with an oily translucent kernel and mild aroma (Table 2). It has resistance to neck blast. □